

ESFRI's contribution
to the planned Charter of
Access for Industrial Users to
Research & Technology
Infrastructures

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The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) welcomes the European Commission's initiative to develop a Charter of Access for Industrial Users to Research Infrastructures (RIs) and Technology Infrastructures (TIs). Drawing on the findings of two comprehensive ESFRI reports - '*Access to Research Infrastructures and Charter on Access to RIs*' and '*Cooperation of ESFRI Research Infrastructures with Industry*' - this document outlines ESFRI's recommendations for shaping a robust, inclusive, and forward-looking Charter. The Charter should serve as a reference framework, supported by detailed guidance and practical tools, to foster effective and sustainable industrial engagement with European RIs and TIs.

The Charter promotes industry access to Research Infrastructures in order to conduct innovative research and development, to increase diffusion of results of basic research in technical applications, and to enhance the trust of industry players in cooperating with research and technology infrastructures.

1. PRINCIPLES FOR INDUSTRIAL ACCESS

The Charter should recognise and support a diversity of access modes to accommodate the varied needs of industrial users. Flexibility and clarity are essential. While the Charter should remain concise and non-prescriptive, it must be complemented by a dedicated portal offering templates, case studies, and detailed guidance to support implementation and usage.

In addition to the existing market-driven wide access modes as stipulated by the Charter on Access to RIs, that are at times also excellence-driven, ESFRI recommends the inclusion of the following:

- Priority-driven access for strategic sectors such as green technologies, quantum computing, and health innovation.
- Crisis access to address urgent societal or economic challenges.
- Training access to support skills development and workforce upskilling.

Principles of how priority is defined, and crisis access is granted should be part of access policies and transparently communicated. Proposals for the access modes above are rather assessed on technological relevance, innovation potential, or societal impact rather than scientific excellence. All potential users (academic, public, or industry) should, within reason, have equal opportunity to access and where possible, should be based on the same criteria - adjusted for access type. While exact and similar criteria may not be possible for different user types, we consider that care should be taken in ensuring that business and academic needs are met.

2. LEGAL, INSTITUTIONAL, AND FINANCIAL CONSIDERATIONS

Legal uncertainties around intellectual property rights (IPR), data protection and liability in addition to current state aid regulations remain significant barriers to industrial/private sector access. Institutionally, distributed RIs - particularly ERICs - require greater visibility and recognition within national research systems to facilitate access and funding eligibility. The Charter should advocate for the integration of RIs into national training programs and innovation ecosystems.

It is important to note that open science⁷ and open access⁸ aim to foster transparency, collaboration, and the broad dissemination of research outputs, while fully respecting intellectual property rights and contractual obligations. These principles do not compromise proprietary arrangements, co-development agreements, or the ability to protect sensitive data and innovations. Instead, they complement existing frameworks by promoting responsible data sharing and interoperability, as exemplified by initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). This approach ensures that industrial users can engage confidently, knowing that confidentiality and IP protection remain integral to access policies.

**In some instances FAIR may be a more appropriate framework than Open. For example, in cases where industry self-finances the work and resulting data there may not be an expectation for it to be open, which may differ from, say, publicly funded research. If open sharing of research results compromises business models of industrial actors, then the charter must reflect this by providing specific exceptions when it comes to collaboration with the private sector.*

[This can be arranged with time limits on closing or other types of agreements on earnings based on results etc. but will likely require some legal assessments.]

The Charter should promote:

- Transparent access procedures, evaluation criteria, pricing and IP and confidentiality arrangements which are publicly available.
- Targeted legal guidance on IPR, data sharing, and liability frameworks.
 - Industrial users typically retain IP on proprietary results from paid access; shared access models may specify joint ownership.
- Harmonisation of access, IPR, and data policies across RIs.
- An holistic view on the RI/TI ecosystem with a potential future interoperability framework, which allows to respond to complex questions and to develop integrated solutions.

Sustainable and diversified funding models are essential. The Charter should recommend funding models including:

- Long-term EU-level funding for transnational access.
- Adequate funding models shall be found also for remote and virtual access modes.
- Co-investment models involving public-private partnerships.
- Simplified administrative and tendering procedures to reduce barriers for SMEs.
- Significant government aids for national access
- Clarification on State Aid regulations and the impact of such regulations need to be laid out within the charter. Moreover, ways within which the current state aid rules around engagement can be reviewed to minimise the impact on private sector use of publically funded RIs or TIs is strongly recommended.

3. OPERATIONAL AND TECHNICAL ASPECTS

Industry users are oftentimes not expert or equipped in using infrastructure and require a suite of activities to support their needs. Industrial users therefore require integrated, professional services and so the Charter should encourage RIs to:

- Provide full-service offerings including expert consultation, sample preparation, and data analysis.
- Develop hybrid and remote access capabilities to increase flexibility and reduce environmental impact.
- Invest in digital platforms, data stewardship, and interoperability aligned with FAIR principles.
- Implement quality management systems and, for example, recruit business development personnel to support industrial engagement.
- Consider the development of provisions to enable skills with point expertise to provide guidance to business users (e.g. scientific advice, customer like approach of all the staff etc.).
- All access (including industry/private sector use) must comply with EU, national, and institutional regulations – including safety, data protection and sovereignty, and research security.

4. STRATEGIC AND SOCIETAL DIMENSIONS

The Charter should align industrial access with broader EU policy goals, including:

- Supporting innovation through co-development and technology transfer initiatives.
- Promoting sustainability by encouraging green practices and digital transformation.
- Reinforcing public trust in science through transparent and inclusive access policies.
- Ensuring equitable access for underrepresented sectors and regions.

5. RECOMMENDATIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION

To ensure the Charter's effectiveness, ESFRI recommends:

- Maintaining the Charter as a concise, high-level reference document.
- Developing a supporting online portal with practical tools, templates, and best practices.
- Engaging stakeholders, including industry and RIs, in the Charter's development and periodic review.
- Aligning the Charter with EU strategies on open science, innovation, and strategic autonomy.